

Determinant of the Causes of Insecurity in Nigeria from 2012 To 2021

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Abstract:- Nigeria insecurity has taken an ugly dimension recently to the extent that nobody is safe in the country anymore. Data collected for this study (from 2012 to 2021) which were from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) annual report 2021, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) annual report 2021, World Bank (WB) annual report 2021, Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) annual report 2021 and other relevant ministries, departments and agencies (MDA's) revealed that causes of insecurity in Nigeria which include Unemployment, Poverty, Kidnapping, Terrorism, Violence (Political and economic based), Bribery and Corruption, Ethno-religious conflicts/communal clash, Python dance/Extrajudicial killing, Organized criminal act and Assassination are seriously affecting the nation both in national development and growth. In this paper, we shall get the determinant of causes of insecurity in Nigeria from 2012 to 2021 and recommend that the Nigeria government should pay much attention on poverty and unemployment as they are on the peak and many Nigerians are unemployed and are dying of hunger.

Keywords:- Unknown Gun Men, Insecurity, Development and Determinant.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Nigeria internal insecurity problem is not unique to the citizens of the country. Developed and developing countries of the world battle with same challenge. The only difference is that such countries know how to control this menace than Nigeria. Few years ago, (Berland, 2005) presented how the insecurity of the country will look like and also how it will affect the economy growth of the country.

The Nigeria economic and socio-political landscape has been blighted by the endemic twin evil of violence and crime. The colossal failure of successive government in Nigeria to address problems of unemployment, poverty and unfair wealth distribution among ethnic nationalities, sometimes triggered violent crimes, agitation and anger by some groups and individuals. Such crimes include, kidnapping, militancy, armed robbery, bombing, destruction of government facilities and among others. Nigeria is sitting on a keg of gunpowder ready to explode if adequate measures are not taken.

The Federal Republic of Nigeria constitution 1999 clearly states that “The welfare and security of lives and properties of her citizens shall be the main role of the government”. It's quite pathetic that the government has failed this constitutional role over her citizens.

Generally, the high level of Nigeria insecurity has increased the rate of crime and terror attacks in various parts of the country and this has seriously affects the Nation's growth and its economy.. To tackle the national security threat, the government in 2013 allocated huge amount of money to security department and Anti-Terrorism Act was passed by the National assembly in 2011 (Adaleke, 2013). All these efforts prove abortive as the level of insecurity in the country is at the rise and this has made the country to rank very low in the Global Peace Index (GPI, 2012). With these plethora of security measures taken to tackle the problems of insecurity in Nigeria, government efforts have not yielded good result. The problems of insecurity in Nigeria has attracted high rate of unemployment, endemic urban and rural poverty, low industrial output, high inflation rate, very large domestic debt, inadequate physical and social infrastructure and a lot of others (Adaleke, 2013). UNICEF reports show that on daily basis, Nigeria loses about 145 women of childbearing age and 2,300 under-five year olds, making the country the second largest contributor to the under-five and maternal mortality rates in the world. A greater percentage of Nigerians do not have access to health care facilities, pipe borne water, electricity and affordable quality education (Adaleke, 2013). In 1970, the economic growth failure in most developed and developing countries in Africa and America deliver corresponding social goods and solve problems of unemployment, poverty, disease, hunger, illiteracy and ever increasing crimes and wars, necessitated the new thinking, and redefinition of development from economic growth centered perspective to human centered approach (Adagba, Ugwu and Eme, 2012). In this light Berland, 2005 sees broader as development concept that appreciates material and psychological factor which checks people's welfare. Development is the related to a way of helping people so as to maximize their potential and revive their capacity do exploit so as the meet up with their daily need (Andrew and Kennedy, 2003).

(Berland, 2005) revealed that insecurity has to do with anxiety or fear because lack of adequate protections. (Achumba Ighomereho and Akpan, 2013) explain insecurity in two approaches. In the first approach, they define insecurity as the situation of being exposed to danger or threat or harm. In the second approach, they define insecurity as the situation of being exposed to anxiety or

risk. The anxiety here is an unpleasant vague emotion which can be encountered as a result of misfortune. The two insecurity definitions is the main reason why the affected insecurity persons are unable to dictate what will in the next encounter of an hour or seconds. With regards to research context of this study, we define insecurity as a peace and security breach which can come from ethno-regional, economic, civil, historical, social, political and religious which adds to conflicts recurring and may result in total destruction of properties and lives.

In this paper, we present the determinant of causes of insecurity in Nigeria from 2012 to 2021 and from our findings, we recommend that the Nigeria government should pay much attention on poverty and unemployment as they are on the peak and many Nigerians are unemployed and are dying of hunger.

➤ *Basic Definitions*

- *Insecurity*

It a state of feeling unsafe or not secured. In fact, insecurity is the state of being exposed to threat, danger, risk and anxiety. (Igbuzor, 2011).

- *Unknown Gun Men*

Unknown gun men are group of armed men with gun who specialized in killing of people in the south east of Nigeria (Ukeh, 2021).

- *Development*

It is an act of improving the social wellbeing of people, quality of people’s life, human welfare and satisfying the population’s want and need which can be determined using socio-economic indicator. Berland (2005) defines development as quantitative and qualitative improvements in the people’s living condition which are in the national objectives’ line. In fact, the general improvements in the citizen’s wellbeing is called development (Berland, 2005).

- *Determinant*

It an element that dictates the situation or outcomes of something. Also, it is a thing that takes care of what is happening in a particular place or situation (Adaleke, 2013).

➤ *Research Questions*

The study was guided by the following research questions;

- *What are the Causes of Insecurity in Nigeria?*
- *What are the best Effective Strategies for Tackling Insecurity in Nigeria?*

➤ *Creating Database For Causes Of Insecurity In Nigeria From 2012 To 202*

Table 1 Creating Database for Causes of Insecurity in Nigeria from 2012 to 202

Year	Causes of Insecurity									
	Unemployment	Poverty (Million of people)	Kidnapping	Terrorism	Violence (Political and economic based)	Bribery and Corruption	Ethno-religious conflicts/communal clash	Python dance/Extrajudicial killing	Organised criminal act	Assassination
2012	6,360,840	65,861,000	2,083	7,966	1,047	139	10,210	36,981	112,019	11,023
2013	6,464,867	66,241,000	3,717	8,208	2,678	144	19,223	13,419	114,237	11,684
2014	8,179,683	68,984,000	3,921	9,217	3,048	136	50,817	15,983	114,987	12,871
2015	7,930,218	69,123,000	4,026	9,310	4,879	136	52,769	17,864	117,321	13,678
2016	13,319,885	70,024,000	4,557	9,019	5,034	155	13,807	13,679	125,790	15,186
2017	16,234,307	71,674,000	5,033	8,667	5,678	185	38,623	26,876	126,654	15,487
2018	16,783,593	73,360,000	5,672	8,613	6,872	290	39,107	19,864	127,042	15,865
2019	17,341,873	77,900,000	6,436	8,319	7,079	782	30,012	23,056	128,657	16,125
2020	20,228,591	84,857,000	7,895	8,416	10,034	142	11,863	16,987	132,987	16,565
2021	20,891,989	86,675,000	12,678	8,239	13,569	154	57,698	47,875	146,568	24,234

Sources of data are; Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin 2022, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) Annual Report 2021, World Bank Annual Report 2021, <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/NGA/nigeria/gdp-gross-domestic-product>, World Health Organization (WHO) Annual Report 2021, United Nation Development Programmes (UNDP) Annual Report 2021, <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/NGA/nigeria/unemployment-rate>, Poverty and Inequality in Nigeria Publication, 2022, Nigeria Police Force (NPF) Annual Report 2021, Federal Ministry of Justice, Ministry of Police Affairs, United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime Annual Report 2021, National Intelligence Agency (NIA) Annual Report 2021, Nigeria Security Statistical Bulletin 2022,

Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) Annual Report 2021, Defence Intelligence Agency (DIA) Annual Report 2021, State Security Service (SSS) Annual Report and adapted data source from Achumba and Ighomereho, 2013, Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) Annual Report 2021, Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) Annual Report 2021, International Ant-Corruption Coordination Centre (IACCC) Annual Report 2021 and International Ant-Corruption Coordination Centre (IACCC) Annual Report 2021.

II. ANALYTICAL METHODS

Causes of insecurity in Nigeria which include Unemployment, Poverty, Kidnapping, Terrorism, Violence (Political and economic based), Bribery and Corruption, Ethno-religious conflicts/communal clash, Python dance/Extrajudicial killing, Organised criminal act and Assassination were carefully considered in this study, and data collected on their behalf for the period of study (from 2012 to 2021) were from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) annual report 2021, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) annual report 2021, World Bank (WB) annual report 2021, Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) annual report 2021 and other relevant ministries, departments and agencies (MDA's). However, we apply determinant method for solving 10 by 10 matrix to get the determinant of these causes of insecurity in Nigeria.

III. RESEARCH RESULT

Find the determinant of the causes of insecurity in Nigeria from 2012 to 2021 using the table below

Table 2 The Determinant of the Causes of Insecurity in Nigeria from 2012 to 2021

Year	Causes of Insecurity									
	Unemployment	Poverty (Million of people)	Kidnapping	Terrorism	Violence (Political and economic based)	Bribery and Corruption	Ethno-religious conflicts/communal clash	Python dance/Extrajudicial killing	Organised criminal act	Assassination
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2014	8,179,683	68,984,000	3,921	9,217	3,048	136	50,817	15,983	114,987	12,871
2015	7,930,218	69,123,000	4,026	9,310	4,879	136	52,769	17,864	117,321	13,678
2016	13,319,885	70,024,000	4,557	9,019	5,034	155	13,807	13,679	125,790	15,186
2017	16,234,307	71,674,000	5,033	8,667	5,678	185	38,623	26,876	126,654	15,487
2018	16,783,593	73,360,000	5,672	8,613	6,872	290	39,107	19,864	127,042	15,865
2019	17,341,873	77,900,000	6,436	8,319	7,079	782	30,012	23,056	128,657	16,125
2020	20,228,591	84,857,000	7,895	8,416	10,034	142	11,863	16,987	132,987	16,565
2021	20,891,989	86,675,000	12,678	8,239	13,569	154	57,698	47,875	146,568	24,234

➤ Solution

To get the determinant, we let

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} 6360840 & 65861000 & 2083 & 7966 & 1047 & 139 & 10210 & 36981 & 112019 & 11023 \\ 6464867 & 66241000 & 3717 & 8208 & 2678 & 144 & 19223 & 13419 & 114237 & 11684 \\ 8179683 & 68984000 & 3921 & 9217 & 3048 & 136 & 50817 & 15983 & 114987 & 12871 \\ 7930218 & 69123000 & 4026 & 9310 & 4879 & 136 & 52769 & 17864 & 117321 & 13678 \\ 13319885 & 70024000 & 4557 & 9019 & 5034 & 155 & 13807 & 13679 & 125790 & 15186 \\ 16234307 & 71674000 & 5033 & 8667 & 5678 & 185 & 38623 & 26876 & 126654 & 15487 \\ 16783593 & 73360000 & 5672 & 8613 & 6872 & 290 & 39107 & 19864 & 127042 & 15865 \\ 17341873 & 77900000 & 6436 & 8319 & 7079 & 782 & 30012 & 23056 & 128657 & 16125 \\ 20228591 & 84857000 & 7895 & 8416 & 10034 & 142 & 11863 & 16987 & 132987 & 16565 \\ 20891989 & 86675000 & 12678 & 8239 & 13569 & 154 & 57698 & 47875 & 146568 & 24234 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$|A| = 6360840$$

66241000	3717	8208	2678	144	19223	13419	114237	11684
68984000	3921	9217	3048	136	50817	15983	114987	12871
69123000	4026	9310	4879	136	52769	17864	117321	13678
70024000	4557	9019	5034	155	13807	13679	125790	15186
71674000	5033	8667	5678	185	38623	26876	126654	15487
73360000	5672	8613	6872	290	39107	19864	127042	15865
77900000	6436	8319	7079	782	30012	23056	128657	16125
84857000	7895	8416	10034	142	11863	16987	132987	16565
86675000	12678	8239	13569	154	57698	47875	146568	24234

$$- 6464867$$

65861000	2083	7966	1047	139	10210	36981	112019	11023
68984000	3921	9217	3048	136	50817	15983	114987	12871
69123000	4026	9310	4879	136	52769	17864	117321	13678
70024000	4557	9019	5034	155	13807	13679	125790	15186
71674000	5033	8667	5678	185	38623	26876	126654	15487
73360000	5672	8613	6872	290	39107	19864	127042	15865
77900000	6436	8319	7079	782	30012	23056	128657	16125
84857000	7895	8416	10034	142	11863	16987	132987	16565
86675000	12678	8239	13569	154	57698	47875	146568	24234

$$+ 8179683$$

65861000	2083	7966	1047	139	10210	36981	112019	11023
66241000	3717	8208	2678	144	19223	13419	114237	11684
69123000	4026	9310	4879	136	52769	17864	117321	13678
70024000	4557	9019	5034	155	13807	13679	125790	15186
71674000	5033	8667	5678	185	38623	26876	126654	15487
73360000	5672	8613	6872	290	39107	19864	127042	15865
77900000	6436	8319	7079	782	30012	23056	128657	16125
84857000	7895	8416	10034	142	11863	16987	132987	16565
86675000	12678	8239	13569	154	57698	47875	146568	24234

$$- 7930218$$

65861000	2083	7966	1047	139	10210	36981	112019	11023
66241000	3717	8208	2678	144	19223	13419	114237	11684
68984000	3921	9217	3048	136	50817	15983	114987	12871
70024000	4557	9019	5034	155	13807	13679	125790	15186
71674000	5033	8667	5678	185	38623	26876	126654	15487
73360000	5672	8613	6872	290	39107	19864	127042	15865
77900000	6436	8319	7079	782	30012	23056	128657	16125
84857000	7895	8416	10034	142	11863	16987	132987	16565
86675000	12678	8239	13569	154	57698	47875	146568	24234

+ 13319885	65861000	2083	7966	1047	139	10210	36981	112019	11023
	66241000	3717	8208	2678	144	19223	13419	114237	11684
	68984000	3921	9217	3048	136	50817	15983	114987	12871
	69123000	4026	9310	4879	136	52769	17864	117321	13678
	71674000	5033	8667	5678	185	38623	26876	126654	15487
	73360000	5672	8613	6872	290	39107	19864	127042	15865
	77900000	6436	8319	7079	782	30012	23056	128657	16125
	84857000	7895	8416	10034	142	11863	16987	132987	16565
	86675000	12678	8239	13569	154	57698	47875	146568	24234

- 16234307	65861000	2083	7966	1047	139	10210	36981	112019	11023
	66241000	3717	8208	2678	144	19223	13419	114237	11684
	68984000	3921	9217	3048	136	50817	15983	114987	12871
	69123000	4026	9310	4879	136	52769	17864	117321	13678
	70024000	4557	9019	5034	155	13807	13679	125790	15186
	73360000	5672	8613	6872	290	39107	19864	127042	15865
	77900000	6436	8319	7079	782	30012	23056	128657	16125
	84857000	7895	8416	10034	142	11863	16987	132987	16565
	86675000	12678	8239	13569	154	57698	47875	146568	24234

+ 16783593	65861000	2083	7966	1047	139	10210	36981	112019	11023
	66241000	3717	8208	2678	144	19223	13419	114237	11684
	68984000	3921	9217	3048	136	50817	15983	114987	12871
	69123000	4026	9310	4879	136	52769	17864	117321	13678
	70024000	4557	9019	5034	155	13807	13679	125790	15186
	71674000	5033	8667	5678	185	38623	26876	126654	15487
	77900000	6436	8319	7079	782	30012	23056	128657	16125
	84857000	7895	8416	10034	142	11863	16987	132987	16565
	86675000	12678	8239	13569	154	57698	47875	146568	24234

- 17341873	65861000	2083	7966	1047	139	10210	36981	112019	11023
	66241000	3717	8208	2678	144	19223	13419	114237	11684
	68984000	3921	9217	3048	136	50817	15983	114987	12871
	69123000	4026	9310	4879	136	52769	17864	117321	13678
	70024000	4557	9019	5034	155	13807	13679	125790	15186
	71674000	5033	8667	5678	185	38623	26876	126654	15487
	73360000	5672	8613	6872	290	39107	19864	127042	15865
	84857000	7895	8416	10034	142	11863	16987	132987	16565
	86675000	12678	8239	13569	154	57698	47875	146568	24234

+ 20228591	65861000	2083	7966	1047	139	10210	36981	112019	11023
	66241000	3717	8208	2678	144	19223	13419	114237	11684
	68984000	3921	9217	3048	136	50817	15983	114987	12871
	69123000	4026	9310	4879	136	52769	17864	117321	13678
	70024000	4557	9019	5034	155	13807	13679	125790	15186
	71674000	5033	8667	5678	185	38623	26876	126654	15487
	73360000	5672	8613	6872	290	39107	19864	127042	15865
	77900000	6436	8319	7079	782	30012	23056	128657	16125
	86675000	12678	8239	13569	154	57698	47875	146568	24234
- 20891989	65861000	2083	7966	1047	139	10210	36981	112019	11023
	66241000	3717	8208	2678	144	19223	13419	114237	11684
	68984000	3921	9217	3048	136	50817	15983	114987	12871
	69123000	4026	9310	4879	136	52769	17864	117321	13678
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	73360000	5672	8613	6872	290	39107	19864	127042	15865
	77900000	6436	8319	7079	782	30012	23056	128657	16125
	84857000	7895	8416	10034	142	11863	16987	132987	16565

$$|A| = 185875680405814563180346050590220090621943808$$

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The research results of this study revealed that the determinant of the causes of insecurities in Nigeria for the period of ten (10) years (from 2012 to 2021) is $|A| = 185875680405814563180346050590220090621943808$

Furthermore, the result also revealed that the major cause of insecurity in Nigeria are poverty and unemployment among the Nigerians. Many Nigerians are seriously dying for hunger while many (70% of Nigeria population) are unemployed and these factors contribute a lot in the causes of insecurity in the country. Thus, the insecurity caused by these factors make business and environment unsafe for people to move around.

V. CONCLUSION

Nigeria is tagged as radioactive nucleus that can be bombarded with economic, insecurity and political neutrons that can gradually undergo disintegration if the reactions are not controlled. The crime dynamism and its sophistication seems to have overwhelmed the Nigerian government; the general living conditions of every Nigerian are truly a nightmares in terms of insecurity. Nigeria has experienced unprecedented levels of insecurity occasioned by kidnapping, cultism, terrorism, corruption, ritual killings, poverty, inflation, injustice and bad governance. The level of violence and high levels of insecurity has continuously been a disturbance to every Nigerians. Unarmed and

innocent Nigerians are brutally killed on daily basis as a result of ethnic, religious, political or tribal differences, boundary disputes and ritual killings for example, 2018 Benue State massacre. The insecurity death toll occurring on daily basis, but worse still, these deaths are forgotten easily and the matter also forgotten as well. The government at all levels are making no or little effort at bringing the perpetrators of these dastardly and barbaric crimes to book. The Boko Haram insurgency led to beheading, and kidnapping of innocent Nigerians. This state of anarchy and mayhem is capable of consuming the economy and the entire nation. The level of conflict, violence and Nigeria insecurity is attributed to bad governance, bad leadership, poor justice system, poor service delivery and poverty.

The determinant of the causes of insecurities in Nigeria for the period of ten (10) years (from 2012 to 2021) is $|A| = 185875680405814563180346050590220090621943808$

Furthermore, the result also revealed that the major cause of insecurity in Nigeria are poverty and unemployment among the Nigerians. Many Nigerians are seriously dying for hunger while many (70% of Nigeria population) are unemployed and this factors contribute a lot in the causes of insecurity in the country. Thus, the insecurity caused by this factors make business and environment unsafe for people to move around.

RECOMMENDATION

The study recommended that good governance and youth empowerment should be embraced so as to tackle the insecurity in the country. Also, Nigeria government should pay much attention on poverty and unemployment as they are on the peak and many Nigerians are unemployed and are dying of hunger.

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